

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVE USE

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of interactive methods in teaching the Russian language. An analysis of some interactive methods is also presented.

Key words: Russian language, lesson, interactive education, interactive method, B-B-B diagram, Cluster, Brainstorming.

One of the demands placed on today's teachers is that they know well the methods applied to the educational process, which have passed the world's experience and are effective, and are able to apply them in practice. For this, it is necessary for the teacher to constantly search, learn and test what he has learned, and himself to creatively change and make additions to these methods.

Many educational methods are used to organize the educational process, among which interactive education and the interactive methods that form its basis are considered particularly effective. Below we will discuss some of the interactive methods used in the teaching of the Russian language.

The words interactive and interactive have the same meaning, and the word interactive is derived from the English words "inter" - "together" and "act" - "movement". Interactivity means being with something (such as a computer) or someone (a teacher) in a co-moving or conversational mode. It follows that interactive education is primarily dialogic education, during which the teacher and student, student and computer interact.

The basis of interactive education is conducting a lesson based on interactive methods, as mentioned above. Interactive methods of education make it possible to use and activate the enormous educational power of students, to introduce elements of competition into the educational process: the mental strength of a group of learners is greater than the sum of the strength of its members (that is, the group the result is always more than the sum of individual results).

Classification of interactive methods

Methods of encouraging mastery of what is being learned
Methods of understanding new material
Methods of allowing thinking about what has been learned

Free writing. Cluster. Brainstorming. B-B-B drawing. A sequence of confused logical chains. Blitz poll. Insert drawing. B-B-B drawing. Teaching guide. Teach each other. Ask each other. Two part diaries. The most basic concepts. The most basic concepts, repetition. T-chart. Classification table. What for? drawing. "Blood day?" diagram. Venn diagram. A five-minute essay. Ten minute essay.

The methods of encouraging learning can be used in the teaching of almost all subjects taught in the general secondary education system. can be achieved. For this, the teacher himself should have an understanding of the application of the above methods. Methods such as free writing, cluster, brainstorming, B-B-B drawing, sequence of confused logical chains, Blitz-question quickly attract students and increase their activity in the lesson. In Russian lessons, these methods should be used first in a simple form, and later in a more complex form, in accordance with the age of the students. Lessons organized using these methods are effective in both primary and upper grades.

The methods of understanding new material are methods aimed at students' mutual cooperation in mastering science, learning by asking teachers and friends what they don't know and don't understand, and teaching others. These methods are considered to be effective not only intellectually, but also educationally, that is, these methods form feelings of friendship, honesty, kindness among students.

Reflection methods are methods that determine the extent to which students have mastered a new topic. By using them, students develop skills such as independent thinking and the ability to compare the knowledge they have learned.

In conclusion, language learning is a complex process for students. Students always face difficulties in learning foreign languages. The interactive methods that we listed above help to overcome these difficulties and serve to increase students' interest in learning foreign languages, especially Russian.

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